

Qualitative Study on Teaching Practice and Siwes as Teacher Training Instrument: Meta Subject Problems in Business Education

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Abstract

The modern teacher is condemned to think out of the box to meet the expectations of the current learners who are exposed to the unending volume of information on the internet at the press of a button on their Information Communication Technology-compliant gadgets at any time and anywhere with little or no assistance on one hand, and age not a limit to the prowess that can be displayed by “learned learners” on the other. Teaching Practice is core in teacher training education, as this is the practical aspect of classroom pedagogical theories learned by the teacher trainee, together with students’ Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), which is to give real-life industrial experience to a student. However, while the Teaching Practice is to enhance classroom skills in preparation for the world of work in the teaching profession, SIWES gives workplace experience to students who are likely to find themselves outside the classroom post-training. This paper, therefore, is an evaluation of the relevance of knowledge gained as a Business Education trainee, the adequacy of the knowledge, and an assessment of the value gained in solving challenges of teaching and the world of work in a business environment given the ability to create consciousness between what had been learned during teaching practice and SIWES and applying same to a real situation which is the Meta subjective cognition ability expected.

Keywords: Teaching Practice, Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme, Meta subjective Cognitive, business education, teacher

Introduction

The Chinese scholar, Xunzi (340 – 245 BC) revealed an adage that; When I hear, I forget. When I see, I remember. When I do, I understand. The purpose is to acquire knowledge not only for one's good but also to develop the essence of education, which is to acquire knowledge for one's good and to develop society. Therefore, a man is educated for the societal good. Sidorkin (2011) while quoting B.F. Skinner said learning is simply from one own individual experience, while according to Vygotsky, working together with a more advanced person seems to trigger faster learning about both the physical world and the social world. Dkhar (2013) described education generally as a form of learning whereby knowledge, skill, and habits are etched out in the minds of individuals through instruction, training, sharing, and communicating. In a nutshell, education is usually a transfer of information and knowledge from one individual to the other. In whatever way knowledge is transferred, the ultimate end of education must necessarily be formative. At the end of the day, it is these formative effects that will shape and help mold an individual in the way he/she thinks, believes, views, feels, acts, and reacts in society.

Business education is a vocational study. The objectives of the business education programme at the tertiary level are to train teachers who can occupy teaching and leadership positions in secondary schools, technical colleges, universities, and training programme. (UNN Students Handbook, 2014). The business education curriculum includes courses such as bookkeeping, general business, office practice, typewriting, shorthand, business mathematics, word processing, commerce,

economics, consumer education, and business law, this blend of courses from accounting, business, and office practice shows the double major status of the course. A major focal point in the curriculum objective is to produce graduates that can fit adequately in the classroom and within the office routine in a business setup. Therefore, the place of Teaching Practice in closing the gap between theories learned in the classroom and practicing being a teacher on one hand and becoming a member of staff within a business setting through the impart of SIWES cannot be overemphasized.

Teaching Practice

Teaching practice is a core aspect of teacher education at any tertiary level of education. Is an on-the-field period for the teacher trainee to demonstrate in a school setting all the pedagogical theories learned in the tertiary institution classroom, thereby allowing the student teacher to bridge the gap between theories and real-life teaching. It is a period of interface between the institution supervisor, the host school coordinating teacher, and the intending teacher in training.

The National Universities Commission (NUC, 2017) and the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2015) have established the following objectives for why teaching practice is a mandatory component of teacher training.

1. To expose student-teachers to real-life classroom experiences under the supervision of professional teachers.
2. To provide a forum for student-teachers to translate educational theories and principles into practice.
3. To enable student-teachers to discover their strengths and weaknesses in classroom teaching and provide opportunities to enable them to address their weaknesses and enrich their strengths.
4. To familiarize student-teachers with the real school environment as their future workplace.
5. To provide student-teachers with an opportunity for further acquisition of professional skills, competencies, personal characteristics, and experience for full-time teaching after graduation.
6. To help student-teachers develop a positive attitude towards the teaching profession.
7. To serve as a means of assessing the quality of training being provided by teacher training institutions.

Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES)

The concept Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES): This is a practically oriented programme aimed at bridging the gap between theory and practical. It is also, a programme to be performed, employing both human and material resources to achieve the objectives of training pre-service teachers to acquire practical skills. This activity aligns with one of the laws of vocational and Technical Education which states that; The Training environment must be a replica of the workplace, (Okoro, 2016). This is a training period for pre-service student teachers to acquire industry experience in their area of study. According to NCCE (2012), pre-service teachers are the candidates who have gained admission to the colleges of education to study a programme or course of their choice for three (3) years; to enable them to teach effectively at the basic education level. The pre-service teachers are candidates undergoing training in the colleges of education for teaching and they possess the pedagogy required in the area they are trained in, that is the knowledge and skills that teachers need for effective teaching, (NCCE, 2012). According to the Industrial Training fund, SIWES objectives include: The scheme is designed to bridge the gap between employers' expectations and the actual performance of Nigerian graduates.

To provide an avenue for students' institutions of higher learning to acquire industrial skills and experience in their course of study.

1. Expose students to work methods and techniques in handling equipment and machines that may not be available in their institutions.
2. Prepare students for the industrial work situation they are to meet after graduation.
3. Make the transition from school to the world of work easier and enhance students' contacts for later job placement.
4. Provide students with an opportunity to apply their knowledge in real work situations, thereby bridging the gap between theory and practice.
5. Enlist and strengthen employers' involvement in the entire educational process.

Meta subjective Cognition

This is the exclusively personal conscious understanding of an item that is devoid of external influence. Is the individual interpretation of a phenomenon, as consciousness could relate to given personal previous knowledge or experience. According to Rivas (2016), conceptual Meta subjective representation (i.e. defining properties in the brain as an exclusively physical system is impossible. Similarly, individual memories of conscious experience must contain information about qualitative and subjective as well, since the concept of consciousness ultimately derives from such information abstracted from episodic memories. The foregoing therefore shows that the place of previous contact, consciousness of the contact, and the ability to refer to that previous experience in solving a present challenge as a teacher cannot be discountenanced. The place of the mind, the brain, and memories are individual-based. Hence, Rivas (2006) further states that the stored bases from which

such individual memories of conscious experiences are reconstituted must also contain elements that cannot be represented in the brain. Both Meta subjective concepts and bases of our memories of subjective experiences can only be stored in a personal non-physical memory linked to consciousness. There must be a personal mind or psyche that embraces consciousness, Meta subjective concepts, and bases of episodic memories of one's subjective experience.

Meta subjective Cognition Issues, Teaching Practice and SIWES in Business Education

Meta subjective concept relates to the personal experience of an individual, awareness of a relationship that was built due to contact and stored in the consciousness, i.e. the memory. At the same time, Teaching Practice is a period of attachment of a teacher trainee to a school as part of further training to demonstrate relevant skills acquired in theories. According to Aglazor (2017), the Teaching Practice is intended to bridge the gap between theory and practice. He further stated that the teaching practice exercise is the culminating point where the relationship among the three major players: the university supervisor, the host teacher, and the aspiring student-teacher interface determines the quality of experience the aspiring teacher will take away. It becomes the bedrock on which the aspiring teachers once certified and employed build their professional identity. Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) is also a skill acquisition period, which is also part of the experience building for the student trainee to bridge theories learned in the classroom with pragmatic work experience in the workplace. Oladimeji, Lawson, Olajide, and Akinfiresoye (2017) further emphasized that SIWES allows students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-life situations.

The knowledge from Teaching Practice and SIWES and its resultant display in Meta-subjective cognition shows that a business education teacher can only succeed in the classroom based on the ability to recall exclusive experiences that have been gained during the teaching practice and consciously applying this knowledge to the present classroom challenges, and at the same time, a business education graduate who finds him/herself outside the classroom, that, in the non-academic workplace, will be able to use the Meta subjective cognition to recall various experiences gathered during SIWES into solving current challenges with little or no assistance. As business educators, therefore, the place of Meta's subjective ability, teaching practice, and SIWES in evolving a grounded graduate that is functionally relevant in the business education profession cannot be overemphasized.

Challenges of Teaching Practice and SIWES in Applying Meta subjective Cognition

A graduate of Business Education at any graduate level: Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) or first degree has been trained and imbibed in all the three levels of taxonomy: Cognitive, Affective, and Psychomotor, hence, is easy for such graduate to transmit knowledge gained in the course of undergraduate education to the classroom or workplace setting, whichever he found himself. However, there are challenges that the trainee has encountered in the classroom as a student, the teaching practice, and the SIWES engagement which is affecting the ability of the student teacher to make effective conscious and deliberate use of the Meta subjective cognition, as this may have been distorted even at its introductory stage, thereby giving the student teacher cognitive recognition challenge right from the start and its recall ability questioned when needed. A business education teacher training programme is a tripartite contract in the course Teaching Practice and SIWES: the primary institution supervisor, the hosting institution supervisor, called the coordinating teacher during Teaching Practice and Industry based supervisor during SIWES, and the student trainee. The challenges of this contact can come from any of the players in the contact which can make the Meta subjective cognition transfer problematic when needed.

The student trainee-centered challenges:

Inability to secure placement institution either for teaching practice or SIWES.

1. Transportation issue.
2. Remuneration
3. Heavy workload beyond the ability of the student.
4. Accommodation.
5. Absenteeism, truancy at work
6. Inability to differentiate between work environment and school environment.

Primary Institution-Centered Challenges:

1. Excessive formalities, i.e. more of fulfilling the righteousness of SIWES than interest in the knowledge gained by the student.
2. Negligence in supervision.
3. Emphasis on the report the student is presenting rather than the ability to display the knowledge claimed.
4. Duration of the SIWES is usually short, as this is disrupted by holidays as it is usually within the festive period, thereby reducing the learning period.

Teaching Practice School and SIWES workplace Centered Challenges.

1. Lazy workers who depend more on the student on internship.
2. Absence of incentives to the student to boost their morale.
3. Few internship openings.

Business Educators' Use of Meta subjective Cognitive Approach to Solving Teaching Practice and SIWES Knowledge Transfer to Post-Studentship

Self-Assessment: through using the Meta subjective cognition process of thinking, a student teacher can personally give a good assessment of his/her ability without being biased and by so doing, engages in activities where he/she is sure of his/her confidence and also develop strategies to improve on his weakness.

Development of cognitive ability: it assists the student in mental ability development and easy understanding of events by conscious thoughts.

Dissuade Impulse actions: The cognitive approach discourages actions before thinking, rather, it encourages well-thought-out analyses of events or actions before they are taken, thereby leaving no room for errors, and where errors are unavoidable, they are minimal and manageable.

The cognitive approach moves teaching from the realm of abstract to physical impossibility to possibility and unattainable to attainable.

Reduces withdrawal syndrome: cognitive approach to learning encourages and carries along all students, irrespective of their learning capability either introvert or extrovert, slow learners or fast learners, as students are encouraged to tap into their cognitive consciousness; previous knowledge, to extract information to solve present challenges.

Ability-Based Learning: since the cognitive approach enhances self-discovery through thinking, students are then able to learn at their own pace and gradually move to the expected pace after consciously seeing the contributions of their colleagues which will then encourage their abilities too.

Instruction Planning: the teacher who taps into the cognitive approach also will be able to plan lessons taking into consideration the learning ability of students and be able to carry all students along in teaching.

Evaluation of students and teachers: the cognitive approach assists the teacher in self-evaluation of the instruction taught and also evaluates the students to determine if the objective of the lesson has been achieved.

Pre and Post assessment: The cognitive approach assures students of their learning state at the start of an instruction, their learning level during the instruction, and also the learning level after the class contact, hence, it will assist in answering self-evaluation questions and how to solve such.

Muddiest point: both the teacher and the learners can easily identify and understand their confusion about a particular phenomenon and assist in how to go about it.

Cognitive strategies

Why and how questions: when the question is continuously asked, it shows that there is a knowledge gap that needs filling or bridging, therefore, business educators and students should not shy from asking questions as this enhances knowledge.

Performance analyses: irrespective of whether the performance is expected or undesired, student-teachers or teachers must assess all steps taken to arrive at the actual result to ensure that the results achieved are a result of honest effort and also to be sure there is no knowledge gap. Question: Is performance equal to effort put into it? so that the feedback will be used for further critical thinking and decision.

Free thinking: learners should be allowed to think freely and assess the result of their thinking, by so doing, if there is a shortcoming when compared with their peers, the learners can make an honest adjustment, unlike when teleguided which will make them to be dependent instead of independent.

Retrospective post-assessments: there should be an after-assessment of the result by the teacher. This is evaluating performance from thinking, correcting errors, and ensuring that reasons for errors are pointed out to the students in order not to confuse them more.

Make learning interesting: right from the first class, pose questions and identify paradoxes that will engage students' curiosity.

Promote a mastery orientation: as students value success, the teacher should define success so that students know when they are below the expectation so that necessary effort toward remedy can be taken.

Student-Teachers Perceptions of the Teaching Practice and Its Effects on the Exercise

Teaching practice is an integral part of the teacher education programme at any level of tertiary education, as is meant to bridge the gap between theories learned by the student teacher in the classroom and the expected pragmatic skill to be

displayed in the classroom after the pre-service teacher period. The student teacher therefore is the recipient of knowledge during the teaching practice, as the other major players: the college/university supervisor and the host school teacher are both mentors, while the student teacher is the mentee. According to Tubbs and Holiday (2019), the stakeholder's perceptions of the practicum experience are most valuable for the continuous improvement of the programme. It therefore shows that the perception of the student teacher cannot be discountenanced if the programme of teaching practice is to achieve its objectives.

In the research study carried out by Tubbs and Holliday (2019), it was observed that participating candidates considered "hands-on" experience and flexibility as the major strengths of the program. In one candidate's words, "Not assigned specific standards at specific times, this allowed me to participate in a wide variety of standards as they came up in my school". A few candidates also mentioned that they had "knowledgeable and helpful" mentors and/or supervisors throughout their practicum experiences. Furthermore, Amankwah, Oti-Agyen, and Sam (2017) observed that student-teachers indicated that the teaching practice programme is good for training and developing teachers. This also supports. Nwanekezi, Okoli, and Mezieobi (2011) investigated the attitude of student-teachers towards teaching practice in Nigeria and reported that student-teachers were satisfied with the scheme based on good experience and therefore should be allowed to continue.

However, Tubbs and Holliday (2019) observed that the main weaknesses of the current practicum as pointed out by the participating candidates included: a lack of communication between students and their institution supervisors, inconsistency in the requirements among supervisors, delay in assigning supervisors and giving directions to practicum candidates at the beginning of each semester, difficulty in getting help from mentors, not enough specified experiences, and too many hours required for each semester. The majority of participating candidates (72%) considered the mentor as very important if he/she "assigns leadership duties regularly". However, several candidates commented that the mentor "must be willing to offer guidance into their daily operations, activities, and leadership philosophy". One candidate wrote that she fulfilled her leadership hours on her own because her mentor was very busy and she hated "bothering her for leadership ideas".

In the study conducted by Amankwah, Oti-Agyen, and Sam (2017), it was found that teaching practice has equipped the student teachers with necessary teaching skills" and then followed by improved teaching knowledge" and also that teaching practice helps trainees to increase their job satisfaction, teaching efficacy, experience, skills, knowledge, and career-long profession. Student teachers were equally satisfied with teaching practice assessment regardless of subject area specialization, Wambugu (2013). These findings seem to agree with those of Alnaji (2020) who surveyed graduates of various specializations about the importance of teaching skills and the extent to which they acquired them in the teaching practice exercise at Mu'tah University. The researcher found that the extent to which they acquired teaching skills was moderate for all of them irrespective of area of specialization.

Given the study conducted by Tubbs and Holliday (2019), the participating candidates suggested the following: (a) regular communication between supervisors and mentors to "make sure the candidate has been given opportunities to do some administrative work", (b) "specific field experiences to complete", (c) consistent expectations across the board, (d) "embedded experience into each course", (e) a slight reduction of the number of hours, and (f) reduction of supervisor's visits to one time or no mandated visit unless needed.

Teaching as a Profession: The Process

The concept of professionalism has been used by different skilled individuals and groups of individuals, whether their skill was acquired formally or in an informal setting, therefore, the term is almost being loosely used. However, according to Hart and Marshall (2019), professionals in the "classic" fields of law, medicine, and theology have codified rules and expectations for behavior developed over many centuries. However, (Tichenor and Tichenor, 2004) affirm that in the field of education, however, being a classroom teacher is not always associated with being a professional, that is, American society does not generally view teachers in the same way as they view other professionals; the belief that "anyone can teach" is not found in other professions. Likewise in the words of Yusuf, Afolabi & Oyetayo (2014); teaching in Nigeria has been patronized by the people who could not succeed in their chosen vocations and the people who believe that teaching is a "spare time job" that allows them to simultaneously engage in other profit-making businesses which they considered more lucrative than teaching.

In Nigeria today, statutorily, teaching has gone beyond "all comers affair" as the teaching profession in Nigeria has been recognized by all stakeholders. In achieving the professionalism of the teaching profession, The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 1990) states clearly in the Nigeria Teachers Manual that, the professionalization of teaching should be given adequate attention to enhance the role of teachers in the formulation and implementation of educational policies in the country. The government, through the National Policy on Education, has clearly stated that "teacher education will continue to be given

major emphasis in all our educational planning” because “no education system can rise above the quality of its teacher.” (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). In addition, the government has recognized teaching as a profession by stating that; “Teaching, like other professions in Nigeria, will be legally and publicly recognized as a profession and in this regard, the government has further taken a step in the establishment of Teacher Registration Council among whose functions are registration, accreditations, certification, discipline and regulation of professional practices as it relates to teaching at any level of Nigeria education.

In an attempt to professionalize teaching, (Yusuf, Afolabi & Oyetayo, 2014) proffered the following: Immediate commencement of work by the recently established Teachers’ Registration Council of Nigeria. As the National Teachers Registration Council has been established through the enactment of Act No 31 of 1993, this national body should be assisted by the State Teachers’ Registration Council in every State of the Federation, to be charged with the responsibility of teachers’ registration, accreditation, certification, promotion, development, discipline and making regulations to control the practice of teaching as a profession. The government should make provision for the professional growth of the teachers through periodic in-service education and this should be sponsored by the government. The government should introduce unified service conditions for all categories of teachers throughout the country. This includes a unified salary such as the much-agitated Teachers' Salary Structure (TSS), specially designed for teachers to enhance their remuneration and welfare package.

The minimum teaching qualification of NCE should be enforced by the Government. Like other professions such as medicine, law, engineering, pharmacy, and accountancy which are highly valued in Nigeria, it becomes highly imperative to review the duration of the teaching practice exercise from a minimum of 12 weeks to 12 months. This will enhance professional development and proper orientation and adjustment of the teachers to the school setting. The teacher trainee should undergo professional training in the colleges of education, university, and other teacher education programmes. The government should categorize teachers into three distinct groups as suggested by Igwe (1992). These categories are:

1. The full professional teachers are to be made up of all graduates with teaching qualifications not lower than the NCE, Post- post-graduate diploma in Education, or a Bachelor’s degree in education.
2. Intermediate professional teachers are to be made up of all NCE holders; holders of Grade I and II Teacher’s certificates.
3. Auxiliary teachers to be made up of all graduates without teaching qualifications and non-graduates without teaching qualifications.

SIWES: The Catalyst for Pre-Service Teacher Performance

That employment capability of the government and the private sector cannot absorb the number of graduates yearly, and that employers are complaining about the employability of graduates is a major recipe for underdevelopment on the one hand and an increase in crime on the other. Sa’ad (2010) stated that the quality of graduate skills is gradually eroded as a result of the distressed economy where funding of education is reduced, and with the high cost of tools and machines, the institution can neither procure new ones nor repair damaged ones.

However, SIWES as a prerequisite for graduates in vocational teach SIWES gives the recipients insight into how micro or small businesses work, as they are exposed to work etiquette in the course of the SIWES exercise, thereby gaining on-the-job experience that ordinarily cannot be acquired within the walls of the classroom.

1. It creates in the recipients the capacity to start a new venture of their own.
2. SIWES builds on the recipient's general understanding of business areas and approaches.
3. It inculcates into the pre-service teachers' enterprising capacity.
4. It exposes the recipient to difficulties and challenges in the operations of the enterprise.
5. SIWES also builds the professional abilities of the pre-service teachers.

Conclusion

Every contact made with either an individual or an object, a cognitive memory is created and as such, this consciousness will always remain in the memory and non-physical and will be required at a later date in understanding a new experience and also help in solving challenges that might arise in the course of the new adventures. Teaching practice and the Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme are both not formalities, but a means towards an end which is the Meta subjective cognition that will assist the students later in life. Therefore, as business educators, efforts should be made to ensure the success of both gap-bridging schemes to enhance better student-teachers and teachers.

Recommendations

Business Education programs should foster stronger partnerships with industries to provide students with practical experience, ensuring the relevance and applicability of skills.

1. Incorporate authentic business scenarios and projects into the curriculum to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application.
2. Include training on essential soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving to complement technical knowledge.
3. Establish mentorship programs pairing students with experienced professionals for guidance and support.
4. Provide ongoing training and workshops for educators to stay updated on industry trends and best practices.

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